

IAC-24-B2.6.6.x87078

SDN/NFV-based Satellite Networks: Challenges and Developments

Hossein Rouzegar^{a*}, Jose Avila^a, Victor Montilla^a, Alessandro Villegas^a, Sergi Figuerola^a, Joan A. Ruiz-de-Azua^a

^a *Space Communications Research Group, i2CAT Foundation, Barcelona, Spain*

* Corresponding author: hossein.rouzegar@i2cat.net

Abstract

Satellite networks, as the most prominent player in non-terrestrial networks (NTN) have recently gained a high priority in 5G/6G communications, to extend wireless connectivity with ubiquitous coverage. Software-defined networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) are pivotal technological NTN pillars in which NFV provides virtualization of the infrastructure resources and network functions as SDN decouples the control layer from the data layer to achieve an autonomous and resilient centralized network. Despite the recent deployments of SDN/NFV in terrestrial domain, it still has a long way to go before deploying in NTN due to the challenges arising from the satellites and space nature. This paper is a review on recent research and developments to address the identified challenges ahead of SDN/NFV based satellite networks including controller placement, mobility management, virtualized network embedding and security issues. Controller placement is challenging in complex systems such as large constellations because of the high number of satellites with diverse capabilities where an optimal multi-layer SDN controller architecture is proposed in both static and dynamic approaches. Besides, to manage the virtual infrastructure of such networks, selecting the main orchestrator is complicated. To address this issue, several scenarios for selecting master orchestrator are proposed on the ground or different orbital layers assessing connectivity, coordination, and resource management. A testbed configured by the main requirements of the ETSI MANO and virtual satellite networks is designed to simulate the scenarios. Mobility management gets challenging in NTN as the high mobility of the satellites over a serving coverage area leads to discontinuity and weak QoS. To address it, an extended MANO leveraging Kubernetes is developed which schedules workload deployments and dynamically orchestrates satellites categorized as master and worker mobile nodes within a cluster to maintain continuous service. Virtual network embedding recognized as mapping VNFs to physical network resources is an issue in NTN due to the highly changing topology of the network and limited resources caused by satellites fast movement. As a solution, hardware reconfiguration and virtualization techniques are leveraged in software-defined satellite payload to ensure optimum resource allocation. As a testbed, two flexible platforms based on a FPGA were tested showing desired results. Security concerns arise as satellite mobility complicates the network configuration affecting the MANO with vulnerabilities such as authentication/authorization flaws, tampering with sensitive data, receiving malicious commands etc. To relieve them, threats are identified and evaluated according to standard security analysis followed by suggested solutions.

Keywords: Satellite Networks, Software-Defined Networks (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV)

1. Introduction

Since the early 1980s, each decade has marked the introduction of a new generation of mobile communication technology, representing a significant evolution in the telecommunications industry's history. It all started with the introduction of first-generation (1G) mobile phones, which were followed by the widespread adoption of second-generation (2G) technology. From a business standpoint, 1G and 2G primarily focused on voice services, gradually integrating

data capabilities in third generation (3G). While 3G faced some challenges, 4G proved highly successful [1]. The initial focus of the 4G framework was to improve data throughput and voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) capacity on a large scale. However, as long-term evolution (LTE) has continued to evolve, additional use cases and scenarios have been gradually incorporated [2]. Today, there's significant anticipation and discussion surrounding the potential capabilities of 5G technology. The telecommunications sector is currently observing the evolution of 5G

networks to cater to its evolving requirements. This surge in demand for advanced services like high-speed connectivity, minimized latency, and the integration of extensive IoT connections is driving the industry towards adopting a more cohesive network infrastructure [3]. 5G heralds a paradigm shift in network technology, offering unparalleled adaptability and scalability to interconnect individuals and devices across diverse geographical locations. Started in 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project) Release 15 in 2015, 5G facilitates seamless network slicing from end to end, empowering the creation of innovative services. These services are tailored to three usage scenarios: enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC), paving the way for a new era of connectivity and value creation [4]. Currently, 5G operates in a Non-Stand Alone (NSA) mode, relying on existing 4G infrastructure. Full deployment of 5G is still underway globally. Meanwhile, the telecommunications industry is already researching 6G, aiming for standardization by 2028 and commercialization by 2030 [5]. 6G will facilitate advanced services like augmented reality (AR)/virtual reality (VR), holographic telepresence, pervasive connectivity, and eHealth. These services will demand much higher data rates, improved stability, increased traffic density, broader coverage areas, and lower latency compared to 5G [6].

The innate constraints of ground infrastructure, combined with economic considerations, often impede the deployment of terrestrial networks in remote or inaccessible regions, including rural areas, deserts, and oceanic expanses. Besides, Integrating non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) with existing terrestrial infrastructure presents a viable and economically efficient solution ensuring seamless and widespread wireless coverage, fostering network scalability and accessibility [7]. Introduced in 3GPP Release 17, NTN is characterized by the utilization of spaceborne (such as satellites in different layers) or airborne (including drones) vehicles serving as either relay nodes or base stations. This configuration enhances the viability of NTNs for extending coverage and delivering services [8–10]. The integration of 5G/6G networks with satellite communications represents a paradigm shift accompanied by technical hurdles. Once identified, appropriate solutions should be proposed to effectively resolve them. In this regard, several projects, including Sat5G [11], VITAL [12], SATis5 [13], 6GSatNet [14], ETHER [15] and SANSA [16] have showcased solutions for integrating satellite networks with 5G/6G technologies.

Satellite networks encounter unique challenges, includ-

ing the dynamic nature of inter-satellite links and the ever-changing constellation topologies. This leads to inefficiencies in decision-making, as individual satellite nodes lack a comprehensive view and centralized data collection. To address these issues, Software Defined Networking (SDN) has emerged as a promising solution, offering improved efficiency and adaptability. Conceived by the Clean Slate Research Group at Stanford University in 2006, SDN revolutionizes networking by separating the control and user planes of networking equipment, consolidating network intelligence centrally in the control plane [17]. It allows external applications to request services through the control plane, while the underlying network infrastructure is handled in the user plane. SDN plays an important role in network architecture by offering abstraction, programmability, and simplified management for various functions like routing, load balancing and firewalling through standardized interfaces. Additionally, considering the growing diversity of services and scenarios, upgrading the satellite systems is an essence. However, due to the limited satellite resources and their hardware-specific features, it is a complex task which requires efficient allocation of network resources. To tackle these challenges, Network Function Virtualization (NFV) offers a path towards streamlined operations and enhanced performance in satellite constellations. NFV focuses on detaching network functions from proprietary hardware. This enables the execution of these functions on general-purpose commodity servers, switches, and storage units, which can be deployed within a network operator's data center [18–20].

The benefits of SDN-based satellite networks compared to the traditional ones are manifold, encompassing dynamic resource allocation [21, 22], centralized control and management [23], streamlined service orchestration [24], optimized traffic engineering [25–27], support for new services and applications [28, 29], and enhanced integration with terrestrial networks [30]. Similarly, NFV introduces several advantages over conventional satellite networks, including resource efficiency, scalability, service agility, cost savings, service flexibility, and improved network resilience and redundancy [31–33]. Consequently, the combined deployment of SDN and NFV technologies in satellite networks promises to deliver these benefits, paving the way for software-defined satellite networks. Leveraging the synergies between SDN and NFV, both satellite and mobile operators can construct networks that are more responsive, efficient, and resilient, effectively meeting the evolving demands of the communications market.

Despite the aforementioned advantages that SDN and NFV offer, they also present a series of challenges.

Some of them include high latency resulting from extensive distances and the computational requirements dispersed throughout the network, bandwidth limitations and resource constraints, interoperability with established satellite communication standards and protocols, security threats such as jamming, eavesdropping, and spoofing, mobility issues associated with changes in satellite positions and handovers, and adhering to specific regulatory frameworks and standards, which may vary across different regions [34–36]. Some of such challenges have undergone examination in research literature, with ongoing investigation into others. Currently, the forefront of attention is on addressing key challenges within research and development, spanning scientific publications and diverse research initiatives. Additionally, the industry has been actively involved in advancing these endeavors through the introduction of various demonstrators. In satellite systems for example, SES, a satellite operator, selected a Network Function Virtualization Software Defined Wide Area Network (NFV SD-WAN) solution to orchestrate and manage its SD-WAN and other virtual network services using O3b MEO constellation and terrestrial connectivity options in 2020. This integration provides exceptional flexibility for traffic management, simplifies network integration, and reduces costs [37]. Inmarsat is also advancing its SDN and NFV infrastructures in ground with routing, management, and security functions being software-defined [38].

This paper reviews recent significant challenges and related advancements in SDN/NFV-based satellite networks. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The SDN controller placement is discussed in Section 2. Section 3 presents the management and orchestration of network resources and services. The mobility management challenges and developments are covered in Section 4. Section 5 presents virtual embedding and resource virtualization issues. Security issues are discussed in Section 6. Finally, the conclusion is drawn in section 7.

2. SDN Controller placement

The SDN architecture encompasses three primary layers: 1) Application Layer which hosts network applications and services. These applications interface with the SDN controller through APIs to establish network policies and configurations. 2) Control Layer serving as the core of SDN architecture comprising the SDN controller. This controller assumes responsibility for centralizing network control and management functions. It communicates with network devices (e.g., switches, routers) via southbound APIs to instruct them on how to forward traffic based on the network policies defined by the applications. The

controller also communicates with the application layer through northbound APIs, allowing network administrators or applications to interact with the network programmatically. 3) Infrastructure or data layer which comprises network devices like switches, routers, and access points. The data plane forwards packets according to the instructions received from the controller, while the control plane resides in the SDN controller [39–41].

The correct deployment of the SDN controller in a network is essential to ensure reliable communication. In the literature, various solutions have been proposed for strategically placing SDN controllers, each aiming to achieve specific optimization objectives, including decreasing delays, maximizing reliability, and lowering deployment costs which are much crucial in satellite networks or unified TN-NTN with nodes located both on the ground or within satellites in different layers [42–44]. Flow setup time, network reliability, network latency, switch-controller latency, and load balancing are recognized as the key metrics employed to assess SDN controller placement algorithms [18]. In the realm of SDN controller placement, research diverges mainly based on where the controllers are located, each option presenting its own set of benefits and limitations. While some studies advocate for ground segment placement, others advocate for placement on LEO SDN-enabled satellite switches [45,46], and some suggest placement on the GEO satellites [47]. Concurrently, other studies propose hierarchical controller architectures, incorporating ground stations, LEO, MEO, and GEO layers [48,49]. Deploying the SDN controller on the ground segment provides advantages like reduced latency, enhanced stability, simplified maintenance, higher computation and storage capabilities and improved cost-effectiveness. Drawbacks are related to limited coverage, vulnerability to terrestrial threats, dependency on terrestrial networks, and scalability limitations. The choice between ground segment and space segment placement depends on factors such as network requirements, coverage needs, budget constraints, and risk tolerance. In traditional networks, SDN controllers are typically deployed in the ground segment to manage the entire network. However, in the 3D architecture which includes terrestrial, aerial, and satellite layers, this approach is no longer practical. The network's complexity significantly increases due to the rapid growth of aerial and space elements compared to ground stations. Consequently, relying solely on ground segment SDN controllers to control such a complex network becomes impractical and unfeasible. As part of the author's contributions, ETHER (sElf-evolving terrestrial/non-Terrestrial

Hybrid nEtwoRks) project is designed as a multi-layered and unified space-aerial-terrestrial architecture [15]. It is envisioned to provide a comprehensive solution for integrated terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, focusing on global network coverage with high service continuity, ultra-high reliability, enhanced energy efficiency, and reduced total cost of ownership. As some of its developments in SDN, a cross-domain SDN architecture featuring distributed SDN controllers across all three layers is proposed in ETHER [50]. Furthermore, a hierarchical approach is employed, featuring a chief controller in each layer that manages the slave controllers within its respective layer. A master controller in the ground segment gathers information from and distributes information to the chief controllers in each layer.

In addressing the controller placement problem, two modes can be considered: static and dynamic. In static mode, both controller placement and the controller tasks remain constant. Conversely, in the dynamic mode, changes occur in the number of controllers, their locations, and consequently the tasks, in response to shifts in demand and traffic patterns over time [51]. The static deployment is more cost-effective, while the dynamic deployment, though more expensive and complex, delivers superior performance [44]. ETHER aims to identify the best SDN controller placement through static and dynamic approaches, guided by diverse service requirement metrics. Including the aerial layer as an additional focus for SDN controller placement adds complexity, underscoring the requirement for streamlined algorithmic solutions, especially for dynamic scenarios. Given the challenging conditions and limited capabilities of highly mobile platforms like LEOs and drones, the controllers could be placed in GEOs and HAPSs (High-altitude platform systems). This deployment leverages various aspects, for example, by utilizing the wide coverage of GEO satellites, which reduces the number of controllers required. These controllers can coordinate the remaining components of each layer, either through themselves or via the terrestrial domain.

3. Management and Orchestration

Management and Orchestration is required to achieve end-to-end control and automation of network resources and service management across all network domains, spanning from radio access through transport to the core network. Generally, orchestration refers to the automatic selection and control of various resources, services, and systems to achieve specific goals, such as providing a customer with a requested network service [18]. The goal of orchestration is to optimize the use of resources to ensure efficient,

reliable, and scalable operations that can adapt to changing demands and conditions. The ever-growing traffic demands of subscribers necessitate physical network expansions, leading to increased capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX). However, service providers are unable to offset these rising costs by raising subscriber fees [52]. In this regard, it has been shown that NFV as an advanced management and orchestration solution leveraging automation and software-defined principles can enhance operational efficiency, service agility, and overall network performance [53]. In a unified TN-NTN, management and orchestration face several challenges due to the complexity and unique characteristics of both terrestrial and NTN communications. This dynamic network utilizes satellites as mobile nodes providing computing, storage, memory, and networking resources. Some key challenges include [54]: 1) Heterogeneous network integration including diverse technologies, protocols, and infrastructures on ground and satellites which requires interoperability and smooth communication between different domains. 2) Limited computing resources caused by restrictions on satellite payload. 3) Evolving network traffic and user demands requires the orchestration framework to scale efficiently to accommodate growing needs. To overcome these challenges, an integrated ETSI NFV architecture is proposed as shown in Fig. 1. It is an extended version of the standard NFV architecture defined by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) for the flexible and agile management of virtualized network services [55]. NFV framework consists of three primary operational domains: 1) Virtualized Network Function (VNF), representing the software implementation of a network function to provide specific network services and functionalities. 2) NFV Infrastructure (NFVI), encompassing diverse physical and virtual resources (such as compute, storage, and networking equipment). 3) NFV Management and Orchestration (NFV MANO), focusing on the orchestration and management of both physical and software resources and VNF lifecycle management.

By overseeing both infrastructure resources and network functions, NFV MANO enables operators to maximize resource efficiency and provide superior service quality [56]. It comprises an architectural framework designed to manage the NFVI and orchestrate the allocation of resources required by network services and VNFs. This framework consists of three primary functional blocks: 1) Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) to control and manage the computational, storage, and network resources within the NFVI. VIM ensures efficient resource allocation and utilization to support the deployment and operation of VNFs.

2) VNF Manager (VNFM) responsible for the lifecycle management of VNF instances. VNFM handles tasks such as VNF instantiation, scaling, monitoring, and decommissioning, ensuring that VNFs operate correctly and efficiently throughout their lifecycle. 3) NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) for orchestrating NFVI resources across multiple VIMs and managing the lifecycle of network services. NFVO coordinates the provisioning and configuration of network services, optimizing resource allocation and ensuring service performance and availability. Additionally, the Operating/Business Support System (OSS/BSS) encompasses operational and business processes not explicitly covered in the NFV-MANO framework.

Different virtualization approaches can be used to support VNFs including Virtual Machines (VMs) and containers. Considering the performance aspects, containers are currently a preferred solution, as they deliver a lighter-weight virtualization technology and better run time performance in terms of throughput and delay compared to VMs [57].

A practical approach within this framework involves placing the satellite cluster within the NFVI and leveraging Open-Source MANO (OSM) along with Kubernetes. OSM functions as both the NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) and the Virtual Network Function Manager (VNFM). As the NFVO, OSM is responsible for the deployment of network services and VNFs. Additionally, in its role as VNFM, OSM oversees the lifecycle management of virtualized network functions, ensuring their continuous monitoring and maintenance [58]. While OSM handles the management of VNFs, Kubernetes operates as the VIM. As an open-source container orchestration platform, Kubernetes automates the deployment, scaling, and load balancing of containers, organizing them into logical units for easier management [59]. The collaboration between OSM and Kubernetes creates a highly efficient orchestration system. This integrated approach maximizes resource utilization, supports dynamic service scaling, ensures high availability, and effectively manages the specific challenges of orchestrating satellite clusters.

To manage the overall network resources, it is required to deploy the main orchestrator. This issue is addressed by considering several scenarios which also help to analyze the appropriateness of the proposed architecture. Each scenario is evaluated through several comparison criteria including scenario architecture components (coordination) and the interactions among them (connectivity). A basic scenario consists of one satellite, one ground station and users on a target area. Satellite runs a Kubernetes master instance as the VIM that interacts with the OSM client at

Fig. 1: Proposed NFV-MANO framework for a unified TN-NTN.

the ground station acting as an interface between the OSM and service area. The satellite as the master node manages resource allocation duties and task scheduling ensuring the overall health and availability of the cluster. This setup enables operators to remotely observe and adjust the configurations. Considering the satellite limitations in resources and QoS, resources on the satellite are managed by the Kubernetes at the satellite as VIM. As another scenario, more than one ground station and several satellites distributed in various orbits constitute a multi-node Kubernetes cluster as a distributed VIM. Regarding the coordination between the VIMs, the master node could be both ground station and a few limited satellites in different orbits. Such a network is capable of inter ground station links as well as inter satellite links ensuring continuous service coverage and more redundancy completed with a database in one of the satellites. All nodes provide their resources in the cluster to support resource management administered by the master node. OSM at the ground station oversees the deployment and logs while ensuring QoS. Analyzing such scenarios lead to selecting the optimal resource management and orchestration architecture in a unified TN-NTN.

The testbed includes the server infrastructure, channel emulator, and Raspberry Pi boards. This integrated setup demonstrates the physical arrangement of the various components. The testbed utilizes VSNeS (Virtual Satellite Network Simulator) [60] simulator which is a novel simulation engine capable to represent satellites and ground nodes in VMs and deploy a virtual network that represents the chan-

nel effects and dynamics. This configuration matches the fundamental requirements of OSM, and the channel emulator, ensuring smooth operation and execution of network functions.

4. Mobility Management

In a satellite-terrestrial integrated network, the connection between satellite and ground nodes whether ground stations or users is always changing. As a result, users previously covered by one satellite often need to be transferred to another satellite with better signal quality and QoS. This frequent handover process increases network management overhead [18]. Therefore, developing advanced mobility management and handover strategies to minimize these handovers and reduce overhead has become a key research focus in satellite networks. SDN-based networks, with their centralized control architecture, can significantly enhance mobility management. This centralized approach provides a comprehensive view of the network and its status, enabling more efficient handover mechanisms. Mobility management challenge has been addressed as an optimization problem with objectives such as minimizing handover latency or maximizing throughput and QoS [61–64]. Besides, the mobility management could be addressed in the ETSI MANO framework. As part of our contributions, this issue has been considered in the proposed NFV MANO architecture (presented in section 3) focusing on Kubernetes.

Kubernetes runs the workload by placing containers into Pods to run on Nodes. Pods are regarded as the smallest deployable units of computing that can be created and managed in Kubernetes. A Pod is a group of one or more containers, with shared storage and network resources, and a specification for how to run the containers. A node may be a virtual or physical machine, depending on the cluster [65]. Kubernetes' ability to manage satellite mobility is based on some of its features including Horizontal Pod Autoscaling (HPA), replication and node affinity. Besides, some custom metrics based on satellite positions facilitate intelligent deployment and migration of VNF to satellites closer to designated target areas.

Through HPA, the response to increased or decreased load is to deploy more or less Pods. This feature adjusts the number of pods automatically according to observed metrics (such as CPU, memory, or custom metrics). Depending on these metrics, HPA can assist in dynamically adjusting resources in satellite mobility management. Node affinity is conceptually similar to node Selector, allowing to constrain which Pods can be scheduled on which nodes according to the node labels. The Kubernetes sched-

uler checks if a node has these labels to determine if it is suitable for running the pod enabling more granular control over pod placement. By defining node affinity rules based on geographical positions or custom metrics of the nodes, Kubernetes ensures that the workloads are placed strategically. By defining the number of desired replicas in replicaSet, Kubernetes ensures that the required number of instances of a service or VNF are always available.

As the satellites move closer to or further away from specified areas, Kubernetes' intelligent control loop evaluates the custom metrics and node affinity rules. When a node's score increases due to its proximity to the satellite's target area, Kubernetes may initiate the migration of services or VNFs to that node. Furthermore, HPA could dynamically scale the number of pods in real-time. By strategically deploying ReplicaSets based on the distance of satellites to the target service area and assigning tags to the closest satellites, the scheduler is directed to deploy pods on these nearby satellites. This approach guarantees that the service appears steady from the user's perspective, even though the underlying hardware infrastructure is in constant motion. These features are implemented within the proposed architecture as the Mobility Manager component shown in Fig .1.

5. Virtual embedding and resource virtualization

Current non-terrestrial networks offer a range of services varying significantly in terms of resource needs, allowable delay, and potential revenue. As a result, flexible service deployment is essential to manage the dynamic nature of these networks. The two emerging technologies, SDN and NFV show great promise in efficiently deploying and managing heterogeneous services in NTN [66, 67]. While NFV decouples network functions from the hardware, improper VNF deployment can increase service completion time, leading to many services failing to complete the execution of all associated VNFs [68]. The Virtual Network Embedding (VNE) problem focuses on mapping VNFs to network nodes and virtual links to physical links to ensure the effective execution of VNFs [69]. VNE has been considered to optimize resource utilization, improve network performance, and provide flexibility in managing network services [70, 71]. In satellite networks, the embedding involves mapping virtual satellite networks (consisting of virtual nodes and links) onto the actual physical satellites and inter-satellite links. A similar concept is resource virtualization which involves abstracting and allocating the satellite's physical resources (like bandwidth, memory, power, and processing capabilities) in a manner that enables them to be shared, dynamically assigned, and

used by multiple services or users as virtual resources [72]. This concept enables more efficient, flexible, and scalable use of satellite resources by decoupling them from specific hardware constraints and allowing them to be managed in a software-defined manner. Virtual embedding and resource virtualization in satellite networks pose several unique challenges compared to terrestrial networks arising from the distinct characteristics and constraints of satellite systems. Some of these challenges include limited satellite resources, highly dynamic topology of satellite networks due to their high speed and varying link quality, heterogeneity in resources and hardware infrastructure, economic and cost considerations and scalability issues. To address these challenges, hardware reconfiguration and virtualization techniques provide powerful tools which can be achieved through the software defined radio (SDR) approach.

Although there isn't a single and common definition for SDR that is accepted worldwide, the key factor in all of the different interpretations is how the radio waveform can be altered by modifying software without requiring hardware changes [73]. Being reconfigurable and adaptable, SDR is accomplished by using programmable hardware or establishing mechanisms to update the software to implement radio functions such as signal processing or modulation/demodulation. By adapting the digital hardware and profiting from available analog front-ends, SDR enables adaptability to new communication protocols and channel assignment policies [74]. current CubeSat missions are typically planned under a fixed-services vision where only limited upgrades are possible [75, 76]. During their design, electronic components and software are chosen specifically to accommodate desired functionalities generating a strong dependency between services and platform resources. To address this dependency, SDR can support the execution of flexible payload frameworks composed of hardware components and software modules, generating an environment that enables the deployment of software-controlled payloads that makes them platform-independent [77]. Flexibility at payload level enables the satellites to reallocate their resources in power, frequency, time, or coverage to adapt to different scenarios creating in-orbit redundancy [78]. In addition to increasing the satellite's processing capacity, it adds interest in risk mitigation, since in the event that the original mission fails or does not have sufficient market demand, the mission can be reoriented by defining new tasks.

To achieve the flexibility, payload hardware requirements include: logic cells as fixed and dynamic hardware, memory, high-performance and low-power consumption

processors, adaptable analog front-ends for flexible RF frequency allocation. In recent years, evolving technologies such as the introduction of Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) System-on-Chip (SoC) and, RF programmable transceiver SoC have facilitated the flexible payload deployment [79]. Flexible payload framework as a technology enabler profits from the advantages of current embedded platforms and small satellites (in terms of performance, miniaturization, diversity, modularity, etc) and the advantages offered by the FPGAs (logic reconfiguration, low power consumption, high computing power) as a specific embedded chip with proven flight experience [80, 81].

As services requirements are different depending on their complexity, the framework offers up to three levels of flexibility: L1) Hardware exchange relying on logic cells reconfiguration, L2) Software reprogramming using modern virtualization techniques and L3) Service orchestration to manage remote deploying of VNFs.

To deploy L1 flexibility it's important to focus on available manufacturer tools to perform reconfiguration. The architectures of current FPGAs in the market integrate a set of different processors in a unique chip to manufacture a complete SoC. With current FPGA technology, logic areas can be totally reconfigured and the system resources where they are mapped can be reused when not needed. As the testbed, two SDR platforms based on a FPGA SoC with logic cells and embedded CPU were selected. For software reprogramming and virtualization of services (L2), containers are flexible software structures that can be deployed over the kernel on a host system using an appropriate containerization platform (such as docker or PODMan). The use of a custom Linux OS is proposed as it allows to automatize libraries installation controlling the size of the final OS. The goal of this software architecture is to containerize all the offered services, so that they can be deployed or retracted on demand under the control of the resource manager. Finally for service orchestration (L3), Kubernetes was selected as the resource manager and orchestrator to manage locally and remotely (from GS) the resources and services.

6. Security

Similar to the terrestrial networks, various topologies of SDN/NFV based satellite networks are vulnerable to security attacks. Among the major security risks in satellite networks are illegal access to private information or eavesdropping, phony control and command messages sent to the satellites interfering with authorized operations and communication, adversary interceptions of both data and control messages during message modification events, and

denial-of-service attacks (DoS) [82]. There can be significant performance costs when terrestrial security solutions like Secure Socket Layer (SSL) or Internet Security Protocol (IPSec) are integrated into satellite networks.

An analysis of the security issues covering both TNs and NTN has been identified and carried out in the 6GSatNet project focusing on an extended ETSI NFV-MANO architecture [83]. An architecture similar to the one shown in Fig. 1 and described in section 3 is the suggested NFV-MANO framework. Finding related threats was the first step towards evaluating the security risks NFV-MANO faces. Microsoft's STRIDE [84] has been used as the threat model, which considers six threat categories (Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information disclosure, Denial of service, and Elevation of privilege) to identify security flaws. After the threats associated with their interactions through suggested MANO framework were identified, the corresponding vulnerabilities can be determined and their severity can be evaluated in order to prioritize the mitigation search. Because of its adaptability and widespread use in the security community, the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) [85] was chosen. The fact that CVSS can score vulnerabilities that impact both TNs and NTNs thanks to its extensive set of metrics is another factor supporting the choice. From the initial analysis, a total of 43 threats were identified. A final selection of 14 threats was obtained by the grouping process, which took into consideration commonalities in scenario descriptions, categories, and common interface usage. The segments impacted, the interfaces involved in the case interactions, the CVSS score, and the string were all taken into consideration when calculating each threat's numerical score using the CVSS. A thorough analysis of the threats that had a score of at least 7 were conducted.

One major threat example is the ability to spoof VIM/NVFI or VNF/EM interface in the ground segment, which can be interpreted as a situation where NFVO/VNFM commands to increase a specific network service (NS) resources are ignored. An attacker can get information about the whole NS catalogue that the NFVO/VNFM deploys and manages by spoofing OSS/BSS. With this knowledge, the attacker can perform DoS attacks from within the NS architecture perimeter by uploading a malicious VNF package or altering the functionality of the NSs (bypassing the authorization controls). In the case of the satellite segment, spoofing a satellite service such as Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) may have a significant impact on the availability of the entire satellite cluster.

A set of security goals have been established subsequent

to the identification and description of security threats aimed at the NFV-MANO architecture. These goals were basically countermeasures meant to lessen the attacks that have been identified. Useful recommendations have been proposed for putting these security goals into practice. The viability of the aforementioned security objectives have been analyzed and demonstrated within a realistic NFV-MANO implementation.

As a total overview of the current paper, a summary of the SDN/NFV challenges and the related developments have been presented in Table 1.

7. Conclusions

This paper presents some of the main challenges and developments of the SDN/NFV-based satellite networks. SDN and NFV, two cutting-edge technologies, present a variety of advantages for NTNs and unified TN-NTNs including resilience, centralized control and management, optimized resource management, simplified and agile service orchestration, scalability, cost savings, and etc. While SDN improves network reconfiguration by decoupling the control plane and data plane, NFV separates network functions from hardware using VNFs. Despite their benefits, they pose several challenges in satellite networks due to the mobility and limitations of the satellites and space nature. 1) An optimal cross-domain multi-layer SDN controller architecture is proposed in static and dynamic modes to address the SDN controller placement in satellite networks which is challenging due to high number of satellite. 2) Management and orchestration of network resources and services in the unified network is a challenge due to the heterogeneity of satellite payload, limited satellite resources, highly changing traffic and user demands. To address the challenge, an extended and integrated ETSI NFV architecture is proposed considering the Kubernetes as the VIM by involving satellite cluster within the NFVI and the OSM as both the NFVO and VNFM. To determine the proper location of the main orchestrator, several scenarios have been planned to achieve the efficient resource management. 3) Mobility management in satellite networks is a significant challenge due to the connection changes caused by the satellites high speed. It has been addressed by a proposed extended MANO architecture considering mobility management in Kubernetes using capabilities such as Horizontal Pod Autoscaling, Node affinity and ReplicaSets. 4) virtual embedding and resource virtualization in satellite networks suffers from limited satellite resources, heterogeneity of the hardware and high satellite movements. SDR approach was proposed to address such issues by hardware reconfiguration and adding flexibility to service

Table 1: A summary of the challenges and developments in SDN/NFV based satellite networks.

Challenge	Development
SDN Controller placement	Cross-domain SDN architecture with distributed controllers in each layer A hierarchical approach with a master controller in each layer Distributing Controllers in GEOs and HAPS to avoid complexity
Management and Orchestration	An extended ETSI NFV-MANO framework Considering satellites as NFVI, OSM as NFVO and Kubernetes as VIM Determining the main orchestrator through different scenarios
Mobility management	Considering mobility management in Kubernetes Using Kubernetes features including HPA, ReplicaSets and node affinity
Virtual embedding and resource virtualization	A flexible payload using SDR approach Hardware reconfiguration through FPGA platforms Software reprogramming using containers through a custom OS Resource and service orchestration using Kubernetes
Security	An integrated TN-NTN NFV-MANO as the framework Identification and modeling threats using Microsoft's STRIDE Evaluating threats intensity using CVSS Security recommendations to lessen attacks

deployment. Benefiting from the FPGA characteristics, service virtualization and on-demand service deployment could be achieved. 5) Security attacks can target various parts of the satellite networks. An analysis of the security issues covering both TNs and NTN has been implemented considering the proposed extended NFV-MANO. Threats were identified, modeled and scored based on their severity. Security objectives will be implemented to lessen the identified attacks.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGeneration EU in the framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (PRTR) (Call UNICO I+D 5G 2021, ref. number TSI-063000-2021-1–6GSatNetGS), by ETHER (GA N° 101096526) of the EU's Horizon Europe program and by the Government of Catalonia in the scope of the NewSpace Strategy for Catalonia.

References

- [1] Ahmed Amin Ahmed Solyman and Khalid Yahya. Evolution of wireless communication networks: from 1g to 6g and future perspective. *International journal of electrical and computer engineering*, 12(4):3943, 2022.
- [2] Wanshi Chen, Xingqin Lin, Juho Lee, Antti Toskala,

Shu Sun, Carla Fabiana Chiasserini, and Lingjia Liu. 5g-advanced toward 6g: Past, present, and future. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 41(6):1592–1619, 2023.

- [3] Ata Sattarzadeh, Yun Liu, Abdelrahim Mohamed, Ruiliang Song, Pei Xiao, Zhiqun Song, Haipeng Zhang, Rahim Tafazolli, and Chuanfeng Niu. Satellite-based non-terrestrial networks in 5g: Insights and challenges. *IEEE Access*, 10:11274–11283, 2021.
- [4] Amitabha Ghosh, Andreas Maeder, Matthew Baker, and Devaki Chandramouli. 5g evolution: A view on 5g cellular technology beyond 3gpp release 15. *IEEE access*, 7:127639–127651, 2019.
- [5] Ahmed Slalimi, Hasna Chaibi, Abdellah Chehri, Rachid Saadane, and Gwanggil Jeon. Toward 6g: Understanding network requirements and key performance indicators. *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, 32(3):e4201, 2021.
- [6] Marco Giordani, Michele Polese, Marco Mezzavilla, Sundeep Rangan, and Michele Zorzi. Toward 6g networks: Use cases and technologies. *IEEE communications magazine*, 58(3):55–61, 2020.
- [7] M Mahdi Azari, Sourabh Solanki, Symeon Chatzinothas, Oltjon Kodheli, Hazem Sallouha, Achiel Colpaert, Jesus Fabian Mendoza Montoya, Sofie Pollin, Alireza Haqiqatnejad, Arsham Mostaani, et al. Evo-

- lution of non-terrestrial networks from 5g to 6g: A survey. *IEEE communications surveys & tutorials*, 24(4):2633–2672, 2022.
- [8] Imadur Rahman, Sara Modarres Razavi, Olof Liberg, Christian Hoymann, Henning Wiemann, Claes Tidestav, Paul Schliwa-Bertling, Patrik Persson, and Dirk Gerstenberger. 5g evolution toward 5g advanced: An overview of 3gpp releases 17 and 18. *Ericsson Technology Review*, 2021(14):2–12, 2021.
- [9] Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network. *Solutions for NR to Support Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) (Release 16)*. 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), January 2020.
- [10] Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects. *Study Using Satellite Access in 5G (Release 16)*. 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), June 2018.
- [11] Sat 5g project. <https://5g-ppp.eu/sat5g/>.
- [12] Virtualized hybrid satellite-terrestrial systems for resilient and flexible future networks (vital) project. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/644843/es>.
- [13] Satis5 project. <https://satis5.urescom.eu/>.
- [14] 6gsatnet project. <https://i2cat.net/unico/6gsatnet/>.
- [15] Ether project. <https://www.ether-project.eu/>.
- [16] Shared access terrestrial-satellite backhaul network enabled by smart antennas (sansa) project. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/645047/de>.
- [17] Huawei Technologies Co. Data communications and network technologies. Technical Report doi: 10.1007/978-981-19-3029-4, Huawei, 2023.
- [18] Weiwei Jiang. Software defined satellite networks: A survey. *Digital Communications and Networks*, 9(6):1243–1264, 2023.
- [19] Ramon Ferrús, Harilaos Koumaras, Oriol Sallent, George Agapiou, Tinku Rasheed, M-A Kourtis, C Boustie, Patrick Gélard, and Toufik Ahmed. Sdn/nfv-enabled satellite communications networks: Opportunities, scenarios and challenges. *Physical Communication*, 18:95–112, 2016.
- [20] Ziye Jia, Min Sheng, Jiandong Li, Di Zhou, and Zhu Han. Vnf-based service provision in software defined leo satellite networks. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 20(9):6139–6153, 2021.
- [21] Jianming Guo, Lei Yang, David Rincón, Sebastià Sallent, Quan Chen, and Xianfeng Liu. Static placement and dynamic assignment of sdn controllers in leo satellite networks. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 19(4):4975–4988, 2022.
- [22] Feng Wang, Dingde Jiang, Sheng Qi, Chen Qiao, and Lei Shi. A dynamic resource scheduling scheme in edge computing satellite networks. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 26:597–608, 2021.
- [23] Tong Li, Jinqiang Chen, and Hongyong Fu. Application scenarios based on sdn: an overview. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, volume 1187, page 052067. IOP Publishing, 2019.
- [24] Nathan F Saraiva de Sousa, Danny A Lachos Perez, Raphael V Rosa, Mateus AS Santos, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg. Network service orchestration: A survey. *Computer Communications*, 142:69–94, 2019.
- [25] Menglan Hu, Mai Xiao, Wenbo Xu, Tianping Deng, Yan Dong, and Kai Peng. Traffic engineering for software-defined leo constellations. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 19(4):5090–5103, 2022.
- [26] Fabián Mendoza, Ramon Ferrús, and Oriol Sallent. Sdn-based traffic engineering for improved resilience in integrated satellite-terrestrial backhaul networks. In *2017 4th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Disaster Management (ICT-DM)*, pages 1–8. IEEE, 2017.
- [27] Fabian Mendoza, Ramon Ferrus, and Oriol Sallent. Experimental proof of concept of an sdn-based traffic engineering solution for hybrid satellite-terrestrial mobile backhauling. *International Journal of Satellite Communications and Networking*, 37(6):630–645, 2019.
- [28] Akram Hakiri and Pascal Berthou. Leveraging sdn for the 5g networks: Trends, prospects, and challenges. *Software Defined Mobile Networks (SDMN) Beyond LTE Network Architecture*, pages 61–80, 2015.
- [29] Luca Boero, Roberto Bruschi, Franco Davoli, Mario Marchese, and Fabio Patrone. Satellite networking integration in the 5g ecosystem: Research trends and open challenges. *Ieee Network*, 32(5):9–15, 2018.
- [30] Ye Miao, Zijing Cheng, Wei Li, Haiquan Ma, Xiang Liu, and Zhaojing Cui. Software defined integrated satellite-terrestrial network: A survey. In *Space Information Networks: First International Conference, SINC 2016, Kunming, China, August 24-25, 2016. Revised Selected Papers 1*, pages 16–25. Springer, 2017.

- [31] Georgios Gardikis, Socrates Costicoglou, Harilaos Koumaras, Ch Sakkas, Akis Kourtis, Fabrice Arnal, Luis M Contreras, P Aranda Gutierrez, and Maria Guta. Nfv applicability and use cases in satellite networks. In *2016 European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)*, pages 47–51. IEEE, 2016.
- [32] Georgios Gardikis, Harilaos Koumaras, Chris Sakkas, and Vaios Koumaras. Towards sdn/nfv-enabled satellite networks. *Telecommunication Systems*, 66:615–628, 2017.
- [33] George Agapiou, Ramon Ferrus, Harilaos Koumaras, Oriol Sallent, Tinku Rasheed, Nicolas Kuhn, and Toufik Ahmed. Sdn and nfv for satellite infrastructures. In *Institute of Electronics, Information and Communications Engineers (IEICE)*, page 0, 2016.
- [34] Shuang Xu, Xing-Wei Wang, and Min Huang. Software-defined next-generation satellite networks: Architecture, challenges, and solutions. *IEEE Access*, 6:4027–4041, 2018.
- [35] Lionel Bertaux, Samir Medjah, Pascal Berthou, Slim Abdellatif, Akram Hakiri, Patrick Gelard, Fabrice Planchou, and Marc Bruyere. Software defined networking and virtualization for broadband satellite networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 53(3):54–60, 2015.
- [36] Taixin Li, Huachun Zhou, Hongbin Luo, Qi Xu, and Yue Ye. Using sdn and nfv to implement satellite communication networks. In *2016 International conference on networking and network applications (NaNA)*, pages 131–134. IEEE, 2016.
- [37] Ses implements amdocs nfv sd-wan package on azure cloud. <https://solutions.amdocs.com/Network-NFV-NaaS-SES-Case-Study-LP.html>.
- [38] Power. agility. game-changing capabilities. <https://www.inmarsat.com/en/about/technology/ground-network.html>.
- [39] Fetia Bannour, Sami Souihi, and Abdelhamid Melouk. Distributed sdn control: Survey, taxonomy, and challenges. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 20(1):333–354, 2017.
- [40] Nick Feamster, Jennifer Rexford, and Ellen Zegura. The road to sdn: an intellectual history of programmable networks. *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, 44(2):87–98, 2014.
- [41] Diego Kreutz, Fernando MV Ramos, Paulo Esteves Verissimo, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Siamak Azodolmolky, and Steve Uhlig. Software-defined networking: A comprehensive survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 103(1):14–76, 2014.
- [42] Jianming Guo, Lei Yang, David Rincón, Sebastià Sallent, Chengguang Fan, Quan Chen, and Xuan Li. Sdn controller placement in leo satellite networks based on dynamic topology. In *2021 IEEE/CIC International Conference on Communications in China (ICCC)*, pages 1083–1088. IEEE, 2021.
- [43] Arled Papa, Tomaso De Cola, Petra Vizarreta, Mu He, Carmen Mas Machuca, and Wolfgang Kellerer. Dynamic sdn controller placement in a leo constellation satellite network. In *2018 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, pages 206–212. IEEE, 2018.
- [44] Shuai Wu, Xiaoqian Chen, Lei Yang, Chengguang Fan, and Yong Zhao. Dynamic and static controller placement in software-defined satellite networking. *Acta Astronautica*, 152:49–58, 2018.
- [45] Liuwei Huo, Dingde Jiang, Wei Yang, and Jianguang Chen. A dynamic migration strategy of sdn controllers in leo networks. In *International Conference on Simulation Tools and Techniques*, pages 19–28. Springer, 2021.
- [46] Dan Xia, Xiaolong Zheng, Pengrui Duan, Chaoyu Wang, Liang Liu, and Huadong Ma. Ground-station based software-defined leo satellite networks. In *2019 IEEE 25th International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems (ICPADS)*, pages 687–694. IEEE, 2019.
- [47] Shuang Xu, Xingwei Wang, Bangyi Gao, Mingwei Zhang, and Min Huang. Controller placement in software-defined satellite networks. In *2018 14th International Conference on Mobile Ad-Hoc and Sensor Networks (MSN)*, pages 146–151. IEEE, 2018.
- [48] Jiajia Liu, Yongpeng Shi, Lei Zhao, Yurui Cao, Wen Sun, and Nei Kato. Joint placement of controllers and gateways in sdn-enabled 5g-satellite integrated network. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 36(2):221–232, 2018.
- [49] Zhan Liao, Chen Chen, Ying Ju, Ci He, Jiange Jiang, and Qingqi Pei. Multi-controller deployment in sdn-enabled 6g space-air-ground integrated network. *Remote Sensing*, 14(5):1076, 2022.
- [50] Lechosław Tomaszewski, Robert Kołakowski, Agapi Mesodiakaki, Konstantinos Ntontin, Angelos Antonopoulos, Nikolaos Pappas, Marco Fiore, Mo-

- hammadreza Mosahebfard, Simon Watts, Philip Harris, et al. Ether: Energy-and cost-efficient framework for seamless connectivity over the integrated terrestrial and non-terrestrial 6g networks. In *IFIP International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*, pages 32–44. Springer, 2023.
- [51] Nariman Torkzaban and John S Baras. Controller placement in sdn-enabled 5g satellite-terrestrial networks. In *2021 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2021.
- [52] Aleksandra Checko, Henrik L Christiansen, Ying Yan, Lara Scolari, Georgios Kardaras, Michael S Berger, and Lars Dittmann. Cloud ran for mobile networks—a technology overview. *IEEE Communications surveys & tutorials*, 17(1):405–426, 2014.
- [53] Rashid Mijumbi, Joan Serrat, Juan-Luis Gorricho, Niels Bouten, Filip De Turck, and Raouf Boutaba. Network function virtualization: State-of-the-art and research challenges. *IEEE Communications surveys & tutorials*, 18(1):236–262, 2015.
- [54] Ilora Maity, Giovanni Giambene, Thang X Vu, Chandrakanth Kesha, and Symeon Chatzinotas. Traffic-aware resource management in sdn/nfv-based satellite networks for remote and urban areas. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2024.
- [55] Oussama Bekkouche, Faqir Zarrar Yousaf, Xi Li, and Tarik Taleb. Management and orchestration of mobile network services over federated mobile infrastructures. *IEEE Network*, 35(6):178–185, 2021.
- [56] Karamjeet Kaur, Veenu Mangat, and Krishan Kumar. A review on virtualized infrastructure managers with management and orchestration features in nfv architecture. *Computer Networks*, 217:109281, 2022.
- [57] Pekka Enberg. A performance evaluation of hypervisor, unikernel, and container network i/o virtualization. *O Virtualization*, 2016.
- [58] Adrián Pino, Pouria Khodashenas, Xavier Hesselbach, Estefanía Coronado, and Shuaib Siddiqui. Validation and benchmarking of cnfs in osm for pure cloud native applications in 5g and beyond. In *2021 International Conference on Computer Communications and Networks (ICCCN)*, pages 1–9. IEEE, 2021.
- [59] Adrián Pino Martínez. Validation and extension of kubernetes-based network functions (knfs) in osm for cloud native (cn) applications in 5g and beyond. Master’s thesis, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, 2021.
- [60] Joan Adria Ruiz de Azua, Uriel López Fernandez, Jose Luis Avila Acosta, and David Rincón Rivera. Virtual satellite network simulator (vsnes): a simulation engine to virtualize non-terrestrial networks. In *74th International Astronautical Congress: IAC 2023: Baku, Azerbaijan: October 2-6, 2023*, pages 1–10. International Astronautical Federation (IAF), 2023.
- [61] Chao Guo, Cheng Gong, Haitao Xu, Long Zhang, and Zhu Han. A dynamic handover software-defined transmission control scheme in space-air-ground integrated networks. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 21(8):6110–6124, 2022.
- [62] Bowei Yang, Yue Wu, Xiaoli Chu, and Guanghua Song. Seamless handover in software-defined satellite networking. *IEEE Communications Letters*, 20(9):1768–1771, 2016.
- [63] Sijing Ji, Min Sheng, Di Zhou, Weigang Bai, Qixuan Cao, and Jiandong Li. Flexible and distributed mobility management for integrated terrestrial-satellite networks: Challenges, architectures, and approaches. *IEEE Network*, 35(4):73–81, 2021.
- [64] Yuanguo Bi, Guangjie Han, Shuang Xu, Xingwei Wang, Chuan Lin, Zhibo Yu, and Peiyao Sun. Software defined space-terrestrial integrated networks: Architecture, challenges, and solutions. *IEEE Network*, 33(1):22–28, 2019.
- [65] Kubernetes documentation. <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/>.
- [66] Omar Alhoussein, Phu Thinh Do, Qiang Ye, Junling Li, Weisen Shi, Weihua Zhuang, Xuemin Shen, Xu Li, and Jaya Rao. A virtual network customization framework for multicast services in nfv-enabled core networks. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 38(6):1025–1039, 2020.
- [67] Guangchao Wang, Sheng Zhou, Shan Zhang, Zhisheng Niu, and Xuemin Shen. Sfc-based service provisioning for reconfigurable space-air-ground integrated networks. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 38(7):1478–1489, 2020.
- [68] Ilora Maity, Thang X Vu, Symeon Chatzinotas, and Mario Minardi. D-vine: Dynamic virtual network embedding in non-terrestrial networks. In *2022 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, pages 166–171. IEEE, 2022.
- [69] Mario Minardi, Shree Krishna Sharma, Symeon Chatzinotas, and Thang X Vu. A parallel link map-

- ping for virtual network embedding with joint load-balancing and energy-saving. In *2021 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom)*, pages 419–424. IEEE, 2021.
- [70] Andreas Fischer, Juan Felipe Botero, Michael Till Beck, Hermann De Meer, and Xavier Hesselbach. Virtual network embedding: A survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 15(4):1888–1906, 2013.
- [71] Gregor Schaffrath, Christoph Werle, Panagiotis Papadimitriou, Anja Feldmann, Roland Bless, Adam Greenhalgh, Andreas Wundsam, Mario Kind, Olaf Maennel, and Laurent Mathy. Network virtualization architecture: Proposal and initial prototype. In *Proceedings of the 1st ACM workshop on Virtualized infrastructure systems and architectures*, pages 63–72, 2009.
- [72] Jun Long, Cong Li, Lei Zhu, Junfeng Liu, and Yimo Kang. Satellite cloud architecture based on resource virtualization technology. In *2018 11th International Conference on Intelligent Computation Technology and Automation (ICICTA)*, pages 125–129. IEEE, 2018.
- [73] Tore Ulversoy. Software defined radio: Challenges and opportunities. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 12(4):531–550, 2010.
- [74] Gianmarco Baldini, Taj Sturman, Abdur Rahim Biswas, Ruediger Leschhorn, Gyozo Godor, and Michael Street. Security aspects in software defined radio and cognitive radio networks: A survey and a way ahead. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 14(2):355–379, 2011.
- [75] G Thomas, S Laws, S Rose, S Stirland, S Amos, and P Jung. Airbus flexible payload perspective. *39th International Communications Satellite Systems Conference (ICSSC 2022)*, 2023.
- [76] Elena Godino, Luis Escolar, and A Pablo Honold. Flexible payload operations of satellite communication systems. In *2018 SpaceOps Conference*, page 2653, 2018.
- [77] Víctor Montilla, Josep Ferrer, Marco Guadalupi, Ramón Antonio Ferrús Ferré, Anna M Calveras Augé, and Joan Adria Ruiz de Azua. Deployment of nb-iot ntn core network functions on software defined radio (sdr) nanosatellites: approach and performance assessment. In *74th International Astronautical Congress: 2-6 October, 2023, Baku, Azerbaijan*. International Astronautical Federation (IAF), 2023.
- [78] Nathalie Font, Cyrille Blossé, Patrick Lautier, Arnaud Barthère, and Philippe Voisin. Flexible payloads for telecommunication satellites—a thales perspective. In *32nd AIAA International Communications Satellite Systems Conference*, page 4382, 2014.
- [79] Mamatha R Maheshwarappa, Mark Bowyer, and Christopher P Bridges. Software defined radio (sdr) architecture to support multi-satellite communications. In *2015 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, pages 1–10. IEEE, 2015.
- [80] Abdulkadir Saday. A review of fpga-based applications and fpga usage in the industrial area. *Innovations and Technologies in Engineering*, page 171, 2022.
- [81] Anwar Ali, Haider Ali, Jijun Tong, Muhammad Rizwan Mughal, and Saeed Ur Rehman. Modular design and thermal modeling techniques for the power distribution module (pdm) of a micro satellite. *IEEE Access*, 8:160723–160737, 2020.
- [82] Ayan Roy-Chowdhury, John S Baras, Michael Hadjithodosiou, and Spyro Papademetriou. Security issues in hybrid networks with a satellite component. *IEEE wireless communications*, 12(6):50–61, 2005.
- [83] Matteo Battaglia, Alessandro Cammarano, Juan Manuel Villarreal D’Angelo, Jose Avila, Maxime Compastie, and Hossein Rouzegar. A security threat analysis for unified network orchestration across terrestrial and non-terrestrial resources. In *2024 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom)*, pages 547–552. IEEE, 2024.
- [84] Loren Kohnfelder and Praerit Garg. The threats to our products. *Microsoft Interface, Microsoft Corporation*, 33, 1999.
- [85] Peter Mell, Karen Scarfone, and Sasha Romanosky. Common vulnerability scoring system. *IEEE Security & Privacy*, 4(6):85–89, 2006.